

FINANCIAL LITERACY AND DECISION-MAKING CAPABILITY ON ADMINISTRATIVE SUPERVISION PRACTICES OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS

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ABSTRACT

School administrators' optimal administrative supervision is often achieved through a combination of professional competence, passion to lead, and a supportive work environment, which encompasses financial stability and good decision-making practices, which are all imperative for a school administrator's overall well-being and effective leader. This study aimed to determine whether the school administrators' financial literacy and decision-making practices have a significant relationship with their administrative supervision. A descriptive correlation type of research was utilized, with 298 school administrators as participants for this study using equal enumeration, mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and linear regression to analyze the data. The results of this data on school administrators' financial literacy suggest they have agreed with an overall mean of 4.09. The teaching decision-making capabilities of the participants were highly practiced. For administrative supervision, the high overall mean rating of 4.10 indicates that administrators are proficient. Among the three variables, the decision-making practices were perceived to have a strong correlation to the administrative supervision practices of school administrators. Among the various factors studied—plan adjustments, goal achievement, teacher interactions, planning, implementation, assessment, and financial reporting emerged as the strongest predictors of administrators' effectiveness in supervision at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, administrators are encouraged to continue prioritizing goal-oriented decision-making while also incorporating a more holistic perspective that includes plan adjustments, teacher interactions, and long-term sustainability. This integrated approach will enhance their ability to effectively guide and support their teams.

Keywords: *Financial literacy, decision-making capability, administrative supervision practices, and school administrators.*

1. INTRODUCTION

quality education depends on the teachers who are the facilitator of teaching and learning and school administrators who are called to bring the catalyst of change in the education system. In educational institutions, administrative supervision plays an important role in management and leadership. It includes how school administrators carry out their duties in improving teaching and learning standards, supporting positive student behavior, and managing schools. Appropriate administrative supervision entails the conveying of information, and the capability to plan and make appropriate decisions in relation to education. However, a quick look at the field indicates that most school administrators receive supervision training, yet many of them emerge with poor financial skills,

which severely affects their decision-making. According to different scholarly studies, insufficient financial literacy among administrators results in pressure on their overall performance in providing resources, and budgeting, and consequently, the poor performance of educational organizations (Arshiya, 2023).

Financial literacy encompasses being informed on matters concerning financial decisions hence is very important for school administrators since they are required to manage both the schools' cash and other resources well. As financial literacy rises, so does the ability to make decisions: administrators are thus better equipped to make their way through spheres of finance (Kumari, 2020). In addition, Financial management in schools involves a broader frame of inclusive

stakeholder participation as required by the Department of Education, with power at the school level shared among relevant stakeholders rather than centralized around the principal (Espinosa, 2017). A cross-sectional study to compare the level of financial literacy among university students regarding their capacity to make sound investment decisions found that financial literacy helped to improve the decisions of the test subjects (Soderlund, and Eriksson, 2020). Additionally, a recent study done by Reddy and Taj (2022) has shown the same trends. This implied that those school leaders who took their financial management training brought better budgeting and resource utilization practices to their schools.

For administrative supervision to be effective, decisions must be made systematically, evaluating options, assessing risks, and making informed choices aligned with institutional goals. Several factors affect decision-making, including the knowledge base, the experience, and the context of the decision-maker. A recent systematic review pointed out that decision-making may emerge as a dynamic process in different spheres of activity and noted that education administrators must face different difficulties and decisional uncertainties (Salehzadeh, 2024). This makes it important to have a clear understanding of both the financial and operational issues because decision-making will involve both surfaces to fit the goals and objectives of the institution. Moreover, studies have shown that collaborative decision-making practices are often enhanced when input from various stakeholders is incorporated (Soderlund, and Eriksson, 2020).

According to Lusardi (2019) due to the knowledge acquired on the financial literacy activities of the administrators, it was seen that these administrators are more likely to support strategic plans that have a fiscal responsibility and are sustainable in the long run. Risk and opportunity identification and evaluation are critical in decision-making processes that satisfactorily meet needs satisfaction and avail development prospects later on in educational contexts. Thus, there is potential for increasing financial literacy among administrators and improving the administrative supervision of schools and their educational performance indicators.

Keeping in view the situation, this study investigated the connection between financial literacy, and decision-making capabilities, to the administrative supervision practices of School Administrators in the Division of Bukidnon for the school year 2023 – 2024. The goal is to provide valuable insights that can enhance leadership skills, improve financial management strategies, and promote effective decision-making, ultimately benefiting the overall functioning and success of the school and its community. Furthermore, this study hopes to provide knowledge and recommendations to the higher authority on the status of their school administrators.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to address the administrative supervision practices of school administrators, considering their level of financial literacy and decision-making capability for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to:

1. Determine the level of financial literacy of school administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1. cash management; 1.2. financial report; and 1.3. savings plan.
2. Determine the school administrators' level of decision-making capability considering the following; 2.1 planning, implementing, and assessing; 2.2 plan adjustment; 2.3 goal achievement; and 2.4 teacher interaction.
3. Find out the level of administrative supervision practices of school administrators in terms of the following; 3.1. job expectations; 3.2. performance feedback; 3.3. knowledge and skills; and 3.4. organizational support.
4. Find out if there is a significant relationship between financial literacy, decision-making capability, and administrative supervision of school administrators.
5. Find out which variable best predicts the administrative supervision of school administrators.

Hypotheses

H0 – There Is no significant relationship between the level of financial literacy, decision-making

practices, and administrative supervision of school administrators

H₀ – There is no variable that best predicts administrative supervision practices.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. *Research Design*

The study utilized the descriptive–correlational method that explains the relationships between two or more variables. This design is also important for giving an idea about the cause-and-effect relationship between variables (Robson, 2015). The descriptive design was used to define work motivation, financial literacy, and decision-making capability regarding the administrative supervision of school administrators. Pearson correlation was utilized to determine the relationship that exists between independent and dependent variables.

2.2. *Locale of the Study*

The study was conducted mainly in the Province of Bukidnon, it covered only the Division of Bukidnon. Bukidnon is a landlocked province. It is located in the northern part of Mindanao, with Malaybalay City as its provincial capital. It is the home of many different ethnic and tribal communities, which are significantly distributed in all areas and mountains of Bukidnon. Thus, education sectors in the province are adverse to the diversity of learning instructions that could cater to different learners' needs and curricula. Most of its schools are situated in remote and far-flung communities, which added impact as to what quality and inclusive education the Department of Education could cater to. Even though the province is significantly called the Province of the Mountains, almost all of its schools, are recognized school for fostering quality education and diverse schools in the country.

The Division of Bukidnon is located in a landlocked province surrounded by Misamis Oriental on the north, Agusan del Sur and Davao del Norte on the east, Davao del Sur, Davao City, and North Cotabato on the south, and Lanao del Sur on the west. It has 491 public elementary schools whose graduates are catered by 66 secondary schools and 49 integrated schools. Noting cultural diversity, the Division of Bukidnon

houses seven indigenous peoples' tribes: Higaonon, Talaandig, Bukidnon, Tigwahanon, Umayamnon, Matigsalog, and Manobo.

Home to 20 municipalities and two cities, the Province of Bukidnon still has several places that are interior by nature and are inaccessible to any transport system. With learners as diverse as the province's topography, the Division of Bukidnon has devised various strategies to carry out its mission of making quality basic education accessible to all. Relative to the situation and with a strong desire to promote positive changes to the lives of the learners, the Division of Bukidnon has formulated its Division Education Development Plan (DEDP) in consonance with DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2022.

The Division of Bukidnon is divided into 47 districts and 648 public schools which comprise 490 elementary, 66 national high schools and annexes, 49 integrated schools, and 43 newly established schools in IP communities. The different offices of the Department of Education are tasked to govern the operations of the kindergarten, elementary, junior high school, senior high school, Alternative Learning System, Special Education, Madrasah Education, and Indigenous Peoples Education. Among the public schools, 489 are elementary, 7 are pure junior high schools, 60 are junior high schools with Grades 11 and 12, 48 are integrated schools offering kindergarten until Grade 10, 3 are integrated schools catering kindergarten until Grade 12 learners, and 43 are newly established public schools in the IP communities. It is composed of teaching, teaching-related, and nonteaching personnel of the Department of Education, Division of Bukidnon as of November 2022. Based on the data from the DEDP (2023), there are 11,059 employees in the division, of whom, 10,077, or 91.12%, are teaching; 495, or 4.48%, teaching-related; and 487, or 4.40%, non-teaching personnel.

2.3. *Participants of the Study*

The participants of this study were the 298 School Administrators of the Department of Education – Division of Bukidnon. They were the School Principals, Head Teachers, and Master Teachers for the years 2023 – 2024. The distribution of participants is as follows: School Principal 128, Head Teacher (I) 82, Head Teacher (II) 8, Head

Teacher (III) 10, Master Teacher (II) 20, Master Teacher (I) 50.

2.4. Research Instrument

An adopted questionnaire was used in this study to assess the work motivation, financial literacy, and decision-making capability concerning the administrative supervision of school administrators.

The research instrument consists of 4 parts: Part I was on personal information, Part II dealt with the financial literacy of the participants: Part III talked about the decision-making capability: and Part IV focused on the administrative supervision of school administrators.

Part II is on the financial literacy of school administrators, the questionnaire was adopted from the study of Supeña (2020). It is composed of three (3) dimensions namely: cash management, financial reports, and saving plans.

Part III – Decision-making practices. The questionnaire was adopted from the study of Macadiron (2015). It is composed of four (4) dimensions namely: planning, implementing, and assessing, plan adjustment, goal achievement, and teacher interaction.

Part V – The Administrative Supervision of School Administrators. The administrative supervision of school administrators was assessed using the Supervisory Self-Assessment checklist adapted from the ACQUIRE Project in 2007.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure

Floating an online survey questionnaire to the respective participants of the study was the primary data collection procedure. First, permission to use the adapted and modified survey questionnaires was addressed to the respective researchers signifying the intent to utilize their standardized material in this study. Second, permission from the Office of the School Division Superintendent to conduct the study and float an online survey questionnaire in the vicinity. The expected participants were answering the link provided and permitted by the division.

It was understood that participating in this study is voluntary and not compulsory. The participants of this study were informed about the study and

withdrawal from participating in the study was respected. The researchers assured the participants that the information obtained from the survey was treated with utmost confidentiality, considering the Republic Act 10173, provision, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The information and results obtained from this study were used significantly in the discussion of results and findings, and formulation of recommendations and conclusions.

2.6. Data Analysis

The following statistical treatments were employed in the study:

For problems 1, 2, and 3, descriptive statistics was utilized to determine the levels of the administrative supervision of school administrators, considering their level of financial literacy, and decision-making practices, such as the mean. For problem 4, Pearson Product Moment of correlation (Pearson r) will be used to determine the relationship that exists between financial literacy, and decision-making practices as independent variables and thus contributing to administrative supervision as the dependent variables. Multiple regression was used to answer problem number 5 which variables affect administrative supervision of school administrators.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Financial Literacy of School Administrators

Table 1 presents the summary of the financial literacy of School Administrators in terms of cash management, financial reports, and savings plans. It revealed that the overall mean is 4.09 which is a high level on all three sub-variables qualitatively described as administrators are literate and they practice it most of the time. It exposed that financial literacy on financial reports was rated highest among the three sub-variables with a mean of 4.11, followed by cash management having a mean of 4.09, and the least is a savings plan with a mean of 4.07.

INDICATOR	MEAN	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Cash Management	4.09	Very literate and practiced at all times

Financial Report	4.11	Very literate and practiced at all times
Savings Plan	4.07	Very literate and practiced at all times
OVERALL MEAN	4.09	Very literate and practiced at all times

Table 1. Summary Table of Mean Scores on the Financial Literacy of School Administrators

These findings show that the administrators' financial literacy varies in many ways. This means that the administrators do not rely on just one variable under this domain but instead utilize all the sub-variables to be literate and practice it most of the time. Administrators' high level of literacy implies that they are financially literate which is a very important skill a leader must have. The administrators are well-equipped with the necessary knowledge in terms of financial literacy. This will help them not to have depleted savings and financial difficulty, which will help provide better needs for the school, teachers, and learners as an administrator. As a person, this will aid them to have a will to live within their means and self-discipline not to spend beyond one's financial capability.

It is believed that financial literacy is essential to everyone, be it personal or in an organization. The skill is necessary to provide a better and smooth flow of operation. If one happens to have financial distress, it will lead to financial embarrassment that may affect directly teachers, learners, and school performance. If an individual is free from financial problems, one can focus and be more productive.

Hung et al. (2024) asserted that the ability to plan financially, budget, save, invest, and manage debt was characterized as financial literacy. Financially literate people are better able to manage their money, reduce risk, and make wise financial decisions that will ultimately enhance their financial situation. As discussed by Macdon and Merlin (2023), both people and society are impacted by financial literacy. Its impact may be felt on a daily level and manifest itself in long-term financial planning and decisions. To make effective decisions in a variety of economic contexts, improve one's own and society's financial well-being, and engage in the economy,

one must have a solid understanding of financial concepts and risks as well as the drive and self-assurance to apply this knowledge.

As cited in the related studies gathered by Espinosa (2018), the idea of financial management in education refers to the procedure that makes sure school administrators allocate, plan, coordinate, and oversee the school's financial resources to meet its objectives. Understanding the school's financial management is crucial to determining if it is run efficiently and whether it can achieve its goals. As the Philippine government meets the budgetary requirements of the country's public schools, the Department of Education outlines the principal's responsibilities regarding financial management in the school. As mandated by the Department of Education, financial management in schools frequently adopts a more comprehensive framework of management that includes all stakeholders. Furthermore, the Department of Education requires all personnel to undergo financial literacy training upon hiring, this gives emphasis on the importance of developing an enhancement program that is not yet implemented and integrated into various trainings of teachers and school heads regarding financial literacy.

3.2. Decision-making Capabilities of School Administrators

Table 2 reveals the summary table of mean scores on the Decision-making Capabilities of School Administrators in the Division of Bukidnon.

INDICATOR	MEAN	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Goal Achievement	4.19	Highly Capable
Planning, Implementing, and Assessing	4.15	Highly Capable
Plan Adjustments	4.13	Highly Capable
Teachers' Interaction	4.09	Highly Capable
OVERALL MEAN	4.09	Highly Capable

Table 2. Summary Table on the Decision-making Capabilities of School Administrators

It is shown that the decision-making capability of the participants is Highly Capable in terms of their administrative supervision with an overall mean of 4.14. The indicator "Goal Achievement" got the

highest mean of 4.19 “Highly Capable”. This suggests that the individuals or group being assessed have consistently demonstrated a strong ability to achieve their goals. The high mean implies that goal achievement is an important and successful aspect of their performance or behavior as school administrators. The lowest mean value is 4.09 which is on teachers’ interaction with the administrators with the qualitative interpretation of Highly Capable.

The decision-making capability of school administrators is indeed a complex process that involves various elements. According to Simon's concept of bounded rationality (Simon, 1957), decision-makers often make choices that are rational within the limits of the information available and the cognitive constraints they face. This theory suggests that administrators may not always make perfectly rational decisions but rather ones that are satisfactory given the circumstances (Bush & Glover, 2014). School administrators face the challenge of balancing goal achievement with educational priorities when making decisions. In addition to this, they must also consider the concept of distributed leadership. As discussed by Harris (2013) distributed leadership emphasizes the sharing of responsibilities and decision-making among various stakeholders within a school community. For principals, this means recognizing the importance of effective decision-making capability that fosters distributed leadership. By involving multiple individuals in the decision-making process, administrators can promote shared responsibility for school improvement, while also navigating the political aspects and processes involved. This approach contributes to a more inclusive and collaborative environment that supports the overall advancement of the school.

3.3. Administrative Supervision Practices of School Administrators

The table below reflects the summary of Administrative Supervision Practices of School Administrators of the Division of Bukidnon in terms of Job Expectations, Performance Feedback, Knowledge and Skills, and Organizational Support. The overall mean score across all the indicators is 4.09, indicating that the administrative supervision practices are perceived as "Very Satisfactory" by the school administrators.

INDICATOR	MEAN	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Organizational Support	4.24	Very Satisfactory
Performance Feedback	4.22	Very Satisfactory
Job Expectation	4.11	Very Satisfactory
Knowledge and Skills	3.82	Very Satisfactory
OVERALL MEAN	4.09	Very Satisfactory

Table 3. Summary Table on the Administrative Supervision Practices of School Administrators

The highest mean value of 4.24 marked for Organizational Support implies that the extent of organizational support offered to the school administrators is “Very Satisfactory.” It suggests that having a supportive organization can contribute to a school administrator's overall job satisfaction and performance. The lowest mean value for Knowledge and Skills is 3.82, which indicates that the level of knowledge and skills among school administrators is still considered "Very Satisfactory," but relatively lower than for the other indicators. Providing school administrators with professional development opportunities could further enhance their effectiveness in their roles by enhancing their knowledge and skills.

The findings were consistent with the research conducted by Lincuna & Caingcoy, 2023 on instructional leadership practices of primary school heads in El Salvador, Misamis Oriental. It was found that these leaders consistently demonstrated key competencies related to effective supervision. Despite high ratings for overall practices, challenges remain in specific areas, such as knowledge and skills development. Furthermore, another study of school heads' administrative and instructional leadership found that effective administrative practices are crucial for improving teacher performance and student outcomes. In the study, school heads were rated very highly in terms of their administrative performance, emphasizing the importance of providing clear guidance and support to teachers (Mandapitan & Rodriguez, 2024). This reinforces the finding that the administrative supervision practices of school administrators of the Division of Bukidnon are generally effective.

3.4. Relationship between Financial Literacy, and decision-making Capabilities with the Administrative Supervision Practices of School Administrators

Table 4 reflects the relationship of school administrators' financial literacy, and decision-making capabilities on their administrative supervision practices.

INDICATOR	PEARSON	P-VALUE
Financial Literacy	0.575	0.000**
Cash Management	0.546	0.000**
Financial Report	0.632	0.000**
Savings Plan	0.285	0.000**
Decision-Making Practices	0.815	0.000**
Planning, Implementing, And Assessing	0.670	0.000**
Plan Adjustment;	0.718	0.000**
Goal Achievement	0.602	0.000**
Teacher Interaction	0.623	0.000**

Table 4. Relationship Of School Administrators' Financial Literacy And Decision-Making Practices On Their Administrative Supervision.

It can be gleaned from the results that financial literacy and decision-making practices have a significant relationship with the administrative supervision of school administrators. The significance is at 0.05 degree of freedom, showing a positive relationship between variables such as motivation level, financial literacy, and decision-making practices. Among the three variables, the decision-making practices were perceived to have a strong correlation to the administrative supervision of school administrators, having a Pearson r value of 0.815, followed by financial literacy with a Pearson r value of 0.574. This means that, given the different variables, they do contribute to the administrative supervision of the school administrators. Further, the data imply that financially literate school administrators might be

able to make better and more informed decisions in terms of their administrative supervision. Thus, the first hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the motivational level, financial literacy, and decision-making practices of school administrators on their administrative supervision, is rejected based on the findings.

Fischer (2023) points out that a study supported by the University of Oxford on financial literacy in schools states that educators need sufficient knowledge of financial strategies to ask the most important questions and work with financial experts. Enhancing their capacity to coordinate school finances well, results in better administrative outcomes as Fischer (2023) states: Further, educators and students in K-12 curriculum in the Philippines have regarded financial education as important whereby studies from the Department of Education encapsulate a financial literacy program focusing on providing financial knowledge to teachers and students that will enable them to make sound financial decisions (DepEd, 2021). Additionally, another dissertation is focused on the engagement of school financial administrators (SFAs) and finds out that their input is essential to providing accountability and transparency to financial managers in budgeting systems within schools (Bogan, 2024).

3.5. Regression Analysis Showing the Relationship of Financial Literacy and Decision-making Capability with the Administrative Supervision Practices of School Administrators

Regression Analysis was employed to model, explain, and examine the relationship between independent variables, namely: financial literacy and decision-making capability towards the administrative supervision practices of school administrators.

Predictor Variables		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.120	.171		.701	.484
	Decision – Making Capability					
	Plan Adjustments	.266	.052	.266	5.093	.000
	Goal Achievement	.183	.037	.216	4.959	.000
	Teacher Interaction	.209	.038	.238	5.487	.000
	Planning, Implementing, and Assessing	.172	.043	.194	3.972	.000
	Financial Literacy					
	Financial Report	.134	.054	.117	2.463	.014

Dependent Variable: ADMINISTRATIVE SUPERVISION

R= .821 R2 = .674 F= 120.573 P – value = .000

*=Significant at the 5% level

Table 5. Regression analysis showing the relationship of Financial Literacy and decision–making Capability with the Administrative Supervision Practices of School Administrators.

Based on the regression analysis, it is shown that the variable on Plan adjustments, Goal achievement, Teacher interaction, Planning, implementing, & assessing, and Financial Report with the coefficient of .120 has a positive correlation with the administrators' administrative supervision. This is evident by the computed t-value of .701 but it has a corresponding probability value of .484, which is not significant at the 5% level.

The equation model, useful in predicting Y, performance of basic education teachers is as follows:

$$Y = .120 + .266 (X1) + .183 (X2) + .209 (X3) + .172 (X4) + .134 (X5)$$

Where:

Y= Administrative supervision

X1 = Plan adjustments

X2 = Goal achievement,

X3 = Teacher interaction

X4 = Planning, implementing, & assessing

X5 = Financial Report

The regression analysis reveals that the model exhibits strong predictive power for the dependent variable, Administrative Supervision, with an R-value of 0.821, indicating a high correlation between the predicted and actual values. The R-squared value of 0.674 suggests that approximately 67.4% of the variation in the administrators' administrative supervision can be explained by the predictor variables, which are the plan adjustments, goal achievement, teacher interaction, planning, implementing, & assessing, and financial Report of administrators. Hence, the other 32.6 % is attributed to other variables that were not included in the study. This substantial explanatory power is further supported by an F-statistic of 120.573, which indicates that the model is statistically significant, with a p-value of .000. This p-value confirms that the results are highly significant, indicating that the predictor variables reliably influence administrative supervision levels.

Thus, the second null hypothesis which states that there is no variable that best predicts administrative supervision of school administrators is rejected, the variable “Plan adjustments, Goal achievement, Teacher interaction, Planning, implementing, & assessing, and Financial Report” can predict the administrators' administrative supervision. It implies that the administrators' administrative supervision has been influenced by their implemented improvement in terms of evaluating and prioritizing school programs and activities.

Supporting this analysis, research has shown that effective financial management is essential for school leaders to meet their educational goals and improve student outcomes. For instance, a guide for school administrators emphasizes that financial management directly impacts student achievement by ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently to support educational initiatives (ESS, 2019). Furthermore, the importance of financial literacy among educational leaders is underscored by a recent article that states that a lack of financial knowledge can adversely affect institutional performance and decision-making (Faculty Focus, 2023). This aligns with your findings that highlight the necessity for school administrators to possess strong financial skills to enhance their decision-making capabilities. Moreover, the integration of financial education into school curricula has been recognized as vital for developing financially literate leaders who can make informed decisions regarding resource allocation (DepEd, 2021).

The ability of administrators to effectively adjust and adapt their plans is a critical determinant of their overall administrative supervision performance. Proper plan adjustments by school administrators allow them to be more responsive to evolving circumstances, address emerging challenges, and align their supervisory practices with the dynamic needs of the school environment. Research indicates that effective planning and implementation significantly contribute to the success of educational institutions. For instance, a recent study highlights that systematic planning and assessment processes are essential for achieving educational goals, as they enable administrators to evaluate progress and make necessary adjustments in real-time (Aada, 2020). This aligns with your findings that strong plan adjustment skills enhance resource allocation and coordination of activities, ultimately leading to improved guidance and support for teachers and staff.

Furthermore, teacher interaction plays a vital role in fostering an effective learning environment. A comprehensive review by Sieber et al. (2023) emphasizes that positive teacher-student interactions are crucial for enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. The study demonstrates that effective interactions can significantly improve students' classroom well-

being, which in turn supports their academic performance (Sieber et al., 2023). By promoting constructive interactions between teachers and students, administrators can create an atmosphere that enhances teaching effectiveness and student engagement.

The findings are also sustained by Day, Sammons, and Gorgen (2020), which elucidate the relationship between the plan adjustments of school administrators and their overall effectiveness. According to Republic Act 9155 or the Basic Education Act of 2001, school administrators play a central role in nurturing both internal and external conditions necessary for developing the school while maintaining positive relationships within the school community. This legislation emphasizes the importance of local governance in education, empowering school leaders to make decisions that best address their specific contexts (Republic Act No. 9155). Additionally, research by Coelho and Gomes (2014) has shown that effective school administrators in the Philippines must demonstrate outstanding leadership skills that positively influence teacher efficacy and performance, as measured by the Results-Based Performance Management System. This aligns with your findings that plan adjustments are a key factor in enhancing administrators' capabilities in administrative supervision.

Moreover, financial management is crucial for effective administrative supervision. A study by Bismart (2023) underscores that financial literacy among school leaders directly impacts their decision-making capabilities regarding resource allocation, which is essential for meeting educational objectives (Bismart, 2023). When administrators possess strong financial skills, they can better assess their school's needs and implement strategies that support both academic achievement and operational efficiency.

The integration of goal achievement, teacher interaction, planning, implementing, assessing, and financial reporting is vital for enhancing administrative supervision. By focusing on these areas, school administrators can create a supportive environment that fosters educational success. By equipping school personnel with financial management skills, schools can foster a culture of accountability and transparency, which is crucial for effective administrative supervision. These insights collectively reinforce the

importance of financial literacy in enhancing administrative practices and ensuring that educational leaders can navigate the complexities of resource management effectively.

5. CONCLUSION

Financial literacy is high, as indicated by the results of the study. Therefore, it is concluded that the school administrators are knowledgeable and capacitated, which illustrates that they practice the skill most of the time. The decision-making capability is specified as highly practiced by participants. The decision-making capability is indicated that it is frequently observed as to their planning, implementing, & assessing, plan adjustments and teachers' interaction but the most prevalent is goal achievement. School administrators' performance in administrative supervision, indicates that administrators are proficient in meeting job expectations, providing valuable performance feedback, receiving organizational support, and have room for growth in further developing their knowledge and skills. There is a significant relationship between financial literacy, and decision-making capability in the administrative supervision of school administrators.

The findings of this study show that factors like plan adjustments, goal achievement, teacher interactions, planning, implementing, assessing, and financial reporting are all important for effective administrative supervision by school leaders. When school administrators manage these areas well, it greatly improves their overall professionalism and leadership skills. This ability demonstrates their commitment to creating a positive learning environment in the school. By demonstrating proficiency in these areas, school administrators are better equipped to respond to changing situations, address emerging challenges, and align their supervisory practices with the dynamic needs of the school community. This adaptability not only enhances their leadership capabilities but also promotes a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement among educators. Ultimately, this responsiveness helps create a supportive atmosphere for teaching and learning, allowing both teachers and students to succeed. By focusing on these key factors, school administrators can build an environment that achieves immediate educational goals while

also setting the stage for long-term success and growth in the school.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that school administrators continue to prioritize goal-oriented decision-making while also adopting a more holistic approach that includes plan adjustments, teacher interactions, and long-term sustainability. Implementing collaborative decision-making frameworks and providing data-driven support tools, along with continuous feedback mechanisms, will empower administrators to enhance their decision-making capabilities. This strategy will lead to more balanced, evidence-based, and impactful decisions that effectively address the evolving needs of the school community. By focusing on these areas, administrators can strengthen their leadership and foster a supportive environment that benefits both teachers and students, ultimately contributing to a thriving educational atmosphere.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Aada, K. (2020). Insight on Planning and Assessing the Teaching-Learning Process. ERIC. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1263944.pdf>
- [2] Arshiya, A. A. (2023). A Study on Entrepreneurial Decision-making and Financial Literacy. Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology. CMR University, #2,3rd cross,2nd A road, HRBR Layout, Bangalore 560043, Karnataka, India.
- [3] Bismart. (2023). Types of Predictive Analytics: Classification vs. Regression. Retrieved from <https://blog.bismart.com/en/types-of-predictive-analytics-classification-regression>

- [4] Bogan, J.M (2024). Understanding School Financial Administration: A School Financial Administrator's Sphere Of Influence And Perception Of Role In Decision-Making Through A Comprehensive Review Of Historical, Legal, Philosophical, And Practice Perspectives On Local Decision-Making And Resource Allocation. Northern Illinois University. Retrieve from: <https://huskiecommons.lib.niu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1035&context=allgraduate-disspractice>.
- [5] Bush, T., & Glover, D. (2014). School leadership models: What do we know School Leadership & Management, 34(5), 553-571.
- [6] Coelho, J., & Gomes, C. (2014). Leadership and Teacher Performance: The Results-Based Performance Management System in the Philippines. International Journal of Educational Management, 28(5), 487-500.
- [7] Day, C., Sammons, P., & Gorgen, K. (2020). The Impact of School Leadership on Student Outcomes: A Systematic Review of Research Evidence. Educational Management Administration & Leadership, 48(1), 3-29.
- [8] DepEd. (2021). DepEd expands financial education in K to 12 to improve the literacy of Filipinos. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2021/07/08/deped-expands-financial-education-in-k-to-12-to-improve-literacy-of-filipinos/>
- [9] Espinosa, F. (2018). Financial management practices of school heads: teachers' perspectives. Skyline Business Journal, Volume XIII-Issue 1.
- [10] ESS. (2019). A School Administrator's Guide to Financial Management in Education. Retrieved from <https://ess.com/blog/articles-a-school-administrators-guide-to-financial-management-in-education/>
- [11] Faculty Focus. (2023). The Crucial Role of Financial Literacy in School Leadership. Retrieved from <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/academic-leadership/the-crucial-role-of-financial-literacy-in-school-leadership/>
- [12] Fischer, D. (2023). "School Leaders Should Be Financially Literate." Retrieved from <https://deidrefischer.com.au/school-leaders-financially-literate>
- [13] Harris, A. (2013). Distributed leadership: Implications for the role of the principal. Journal of Management Development, 32(2), 187-198.
- [14] Hung, L. D. (2022). Safe assets at financial globalization. Journal of International Commerce, Economics and Policy, 13(03), 2250015.
- [15] Kumari, D.A.T. (2020). The Impact Of Financial Literacy On Investment Decisions: With Special Reference To Undergraduates In Western Province, Sri Lanka. Asian Journal of Contemporary Education. DOI: 10.18488/journal.137.2020.42.110.126
- [16] Lincuna, M. L. B., and Caingcoy, M. E. (2020). Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators: the Case of El Salvador City Division, Philippines. Commonwealth Journal Academic Research, 1(2), 12-32. Retrieved from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4315953
- [17] Lusardi, A. (2019) - Financial literacy and the need for financial education: evidence and implications. Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41937-019-0027-5>
- [18] Macdon, G.M. & Merlin, M.M. (2023). Financial literacy of teachers and school heads in the division of Marinduque: basis for financial education enhancement program. Psych Educ, 2023, 10: 1035-1045. doi:10.5281/zenodo.8170154, ISSN 2822-4353
- [19] Mandapitan, I.B., & Rodriguez, M.M. (2024). Administrative and Instructional Leadership of School Heads among Integrated Schools. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14186456. Retrieved from: <https://scimatic.org/storage/journals/11/pdfs/3972.pdf>
- [20] Reddy, C. and Taj, S. (2022). The Impact of Financial Literacy on Personal Financial Decision-Making: A Study Among Students. International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR). DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21275/SR24812010840>

[21] Republic Act No. 9155: Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001. Retrieved from <https://elibrary.judiciary.gov.ph/thebookshelf/showdocs/2/7353>

[22] Salehzadeh, R. (2024). Decision making in human resource management: a systematic review of the applications of analytic hierarchy process. *Sec. Organizational Psychology*. Volume 15 - 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1400772>

[23] Simon, H. A. (1957). *Models of Man: Social and Rational*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.

[24] Soderlund, A. and Eriksson, J. (2020). *Financial Literacy & Rational Financial Decision Making: A Study of University Students in Sweden*. Department of Business and Administration.

[25] Sieber, J., Pöysä, S., & Pennings, H. (2023). Impact of Teacher-Student Interaction on Students' Classroom Well-Being: Evidence from Online Education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), 1-15. doi:10.1007/s41239-023-00320-5.